

STATIC AND FATIGUE CRITERIA IN MULTIAXIAL STRESS STATES
PROBLEMS POSED BY PREDICTION

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ABSTRACT

Tensile-torsion tests of thin-walled tubes are performed on 3 different materials: a unidirectional one, a laminate made out of the first one, and a fabric. Monotonic criteria and isonumber of cycles to rupture loci are reported. The passage from laminae properties to those of laminate, the comparison of laminates and fabrics, and the passage from static to fatigue properties are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The strength of mechanical components made out of composite materials should pass through several steps: determination of the laminae fracture criterion, the determination of laminates (or fabrics), fracture from the initial laminae of which it is made up, and fatigue life prediction. Moreover, all this should be performed under multiaxial stress states because of the material's anisotropy.

Many a criterion has already been proposed for composite laminae; they are more or less accurate, and more or less difficult to identify, but they are presently considered as giving satisfactory answers. The passage from the laminae fracture properties to those of laminates usually consists of using the classical theory of laminates (C.L.T.) to which the assumption of the fracture of the first layer (which uses the lamina fracture criterion) is added. However, this method still waits for experimental verifications. Finally, fatigue gave rise to many a study, resulting in Wöhler curves, obtained in flexural or tensile-compressive tests, but very few results are presently available in complex states of stress.

MATERIALS TESTED AND EXPERIMENTS

Several types of tests, more or less sophisticated, have been proposed for testing materials in complex states of stress. Thin-walled tubes have been chosen, which avoid edge effects in particular. The first step is to choose the tensile-torsion test as it is the simplest one which can be carried out. In this case, the material in the cylindrical coordinates r , θ , z of the tube sustains a normal stress $\sigma_z = \sigma_{zz}$ and shear stress $\sigma_s = \sigma_{z\theta}$ with

$$\sigma_z = \frac{F}{s} \text{ et } \sigma_s = \frac{C}{as}$$

(s = cross section, a = radius of tube)

Three types of glass-epoxy materials have been tested.

- A. A unidirectional material with $\theta = 45^\circ$, labelled U.D. (θ = winding angle of fibres with respect to the axis of the tube).
- B. A laminate (+45, -45) labelled S.
- C. A fabric (+45, -45) labelled C.

All the tubes are constructed by filamentary winding, and are made up of 6 laminae.

The glass fibres, the resin and the curing are identical, as is the relative volume of the fibres ($v_f = 0.6$). This allows the comparison of the properties of the laminate with those of the unidirectional material, and those of the fabric.

All the tests (monotonic and fatigue) are carried out under proportional loading ($\sigma_s/\sigma_z = \lambda$). In the case of tests under monotonic loading, the objective is to determine the intersection of fracture criterion (in the stress space) with the plane σ_s, σ_z . To do this, loadings with various λ values between $-\infty$ and $+\infty$ are carried out. (The sign of σ_s is an important parameter in the case of the material U.D.; the sign of σ_z can play an important role in the case of composite materials.)

In fatigue tests, curves with a fixed number of cycles to fracture are constructed in the plane σ_s, σ_z . A series of tests are then carried out for $-\infty < \lambda < +\infty$.

STATIC EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the experimental points obtained for the fracture in tensile-torsion of thin-walled tubes in the plane σ_z, σ_s , under proportional loadings. The material distinguishes shear stress $\sigma_s > 0$ (in principal axes of stress, which are also the principal axes of anisotropy of the material, σ_s splits under tension parallel to the fibres, and compression perpendicular to the fibres), from $\sigma_s < 0$ (tension perpendicular to the fibres, compression along the fibres). It also distinguishes the values $\sigma_z > 0$ from the values $\sigma_z < 0$. Tsai-Wu's criterion is made necessary by the results^{1,2}. Under plane stresses, in principal axes of the tube, it is written:

$$(1) F_z \sigma_z + F_s \sigma_s + F_{yy} \sigma_y^2 + F_{ss} \sigma_s^2 + 2F_{ys} \sigma_y \sigma_s = 1$$

A representative curve of (1) is plotted on Fig. 1 for an identified set of F parameters. Comparison with the experimental measurements leads to a very satisfactory result.

Fig. 1: UD Material
 \circ : Experimental points
 1: Tsai-Wu's adjustment
 2: Reinforced C_R criterion

Fig. 2: S Material
 \circ : Experimental points
 1: Tsai-Wu's adjustment
 2: Prediction of first ply fracture hypothesis

Figs 2 and 3 are similar to Fig. 1 for materials S and C respectively. It must be noted in these cases that the tubes no longer distinguish $\sigma_s > 0$ from $\sigma_s < 0$ (σ_s is in

noted in these cases that the tubes no longer distinguish $\sigma_s > 0$ from $\sigma_s < 0$ (σ_s is in this case the mean shear stress in the laminate, or, if the C.L.T. is used, the generalised stress N_{12}).

In the axes of the tube, the criterion is, therefore, written more simply:

$$(2) \quad F_z \sigma_z + F_{zz} \sigma_z^2 + F_{ss} \sigma_s^2 = 1$$

The shape of the representative curve of (2) is very different to that of (1). As for material U.D., in the case of materials S and C the simulation of the criterion by means of (2) gives good results, after identification. Tsai-Wu's criterion therefore fits our results exactly.

Fig. 3: C Material - Comparison with S material
 \diamond : Experimental points
 1: C material
 2: S material

ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF A UNIDIRECTIONAL MATERIAL TO PREDICT FOR A LAMINATE

1. Hypothesis of Fracture of the First Layer

The criteria in principal axes of anisotropy are written for the unidirectional material:

$$(3) \quad F_1 \sigma_1 + F_2 \sigma_2 + F_{11} \sigma_1^2 + F_{22} \sigma_2^2 + 2F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + F_{66} \sigma_6^2 = 1$$

It is noted that there are 6 coefficients to be determined, whilst in (1) there are only 5, stress in the material having 3 components: σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_6 (classic notation).

Results obtained from glass-epoxy tubes have, therefore, been used, at 0° in tensile-torsion tests by Atcholi² to complete the experimental results. Table 1 gives these values.

Table 1

F_1	F_2	F_{11}	F_{22}	F_{66}	F_{12}
-3.24×10^{-4}	2.02×10^{-2}	1.24×10^{-6}	2.09×10^{-4}	2.29×10^{-4}	4.89×10^{-6}

The classical laminate theory (labelled C.L.T. from this point) therefore allows us to determine the state of stress in each layer at $+45^\circ$ and at -45° in material S from a tensile-torsion test on thin-walled tubes.

The static fracture criterion of material S can, therefore, be determined from the criterion of material U.D. if a hypothesis is given on the fracture of the laminate.

Amongst the numerous methods of prediction of laminates, the hypothesis is that the laminate breaks as soon as a layer is broken. The corresponding load is spread out in the plane of the fracture across the other layers. In S, as soon as a layer breaks, it is likely that the same thing will happen to the other 2 identical layers. This hypothesis is, therefore, plausible.

On Fig. 2, the predictions obtained by this hypothesis and the values of Table 1 are plotted. It is noticeable that this method leads to predictions which are far too conservative; serious differences exist between predictions and results, particularly on the σ_s axis. This method should, therefore, be ruled out.

2. Effect of Reinforcement by Stratification

The above-mentioned results may be explained in the following manner. The fracture behaviour of a unidirectional material differs depending on whether it is tested alone, or incorporated in a laminate. In the first case, a crack parallel to the fibres is free from propagation (indeed, helicoidal cracks may be observed on material U.D.), whilst in the second case, adjacent layers constitute crack arrests; so the ply can reach higher levels of damage before fracture. This reinforcement effect may, therefore, be determined by calculating the criterion of material U.D. (labelled C_R), such that, when used in the method described in paragraph 1 (with the hypothesis of first-layer crack and the C.L.T.), would lead to a prediction of the criterion for material S in accordance with the experimental results. The details of this method are not given³. The criterion C_R has been superimposed on the criterion measured on the single ply U.D. in Fig. 1. The difference observed corresponds to the reinforcement effect by the adjacent layers at 90° to the first.

3. Another Hypothesis

The hypothesis of the cracking of the first layer can be improved by supposing that this does not lead to the cracking of the laminate, but to a partial transfer of the load on neighbouring layers. For example, the cracking of a layer parallel to its fibres provokes the transfer of σ_2 (normal component to the crack) to the adjacent layer, the broken layer is still capable of supporting the same σ_1 and σ_6 (Fig. 4). Loading can be continued, therefore, until the adjacent layer cracks perpendicular to its fibres. (This provokes the fracture of material S which is made up of only 2 types of layers.)

A calculation of the same type as is mentioned in paragraph 1 leads to the results shown in Fig. 5. A definite improvement of the prediction is obtained in comparison with the hypothesis of the cracking of the first layer. The prediction could probably progress further through refinement of the hypotheses (the cracking of the first layer leading, for example, to a partial transfer of σ_6).

Fig. 4: Other hypothesis - partial transfer of the load after fracture of a layer parallel to the fibres

Fig. 5: Prediction with hypothesis of Fig. 4 and comparison to experiments

4. Conclusions

The hypothesis of the cracking of the first layer, frequently used in the methods of prediction of laminates, is contradicted by experiments in complex stress states. The methods of type 2 or 3 suppose that some improvements, either for the study of the reinforcement mechanism (in paragraph 2 it is in fact deduced from tests on material S), or for the refinement of hypotheses, can be made.

FATIGUE UNDER COMPLEX STRESS STATES

In the case of fatigue, the analogue of fracture criteria is made up of curves, in the plane σ_z , σ_s , along which the number of cycles to fracture is constant: these are called isonumber of cycles to fracture (I.N.C.F.) curves.

The objective is the same as in the static study. However, the first step must be to consider the passage from static criteria to the I.N.C.F. curves. The difference in the static behaviour of the material when it is subjected to $\sigma_z > 0$ and $\sigma_z < 0$ leads to 2 types of fatigue tests.

1. R = 0 Cycles

The material is put under stress between $\sigma_z = 0$, $\sigma_s = 0$ and $\sigma_z = \sigma_{zM}$, $\sigma_s = \sigma_{sM}$. The loading is proportional, i.e. $\frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_z} = \frac{\sigma_{sM}}{\sigma_{zM}} = \lambda$ in the course of a cycle. Wölher curves are traced as several tests are carried out at constant λ and variable σ_{zM} (therefore σ_{sM}). Several Wölher curves are constructed as λ varies between 0 and ∞ .

Fig. 6 shows the results obtained in the case of material U.D.

It is observed that the above I.N.C.F. loci can be deduced from the static fracture criterion through homothetic relationships for the 3 materials U.D., S and C.

The following relationships are actually obtained for the I.N.C.F. curves:

$$(4) \quad TW'(\sigma_{zM}, \sigma_{sM}, N_R) = 1 - B \times \text{Log}(4N_R)$$

$$(5) \quad TW'(\sigma_{zM}, \sigma_{sM}, N_R) = TW(\sigma_{zM} - T_z(N_R), \sigma_{sM} - T_s(N_R))$$

where $TW(\sigma_z, \sigma_s)$ is the Tsai-Wu function as given by equations (1) or (2); (4) and (5) show that the I.N.C.F. curves are obtained from the static criterion through an homothetic transformation (term $1 - B \times \text{Log}(4N_R)$) and a translation (T_z and T_s) depending on N_R .

Analogous relationships are found for material C⁴.

2. R = -1 Cycles

The cycles are between $\sigma_y = -\sigma_{yM}$, $\sigma_s = -\sigma_{sM}$ and $\sigma_y = \sigma_{yM}$, $\sigma_s = \sigma_{sM}$. This case leads to more complex results, as the static failure criterion is not the same in tensile and compressive states of stress (the damage mechanisms are different), and as plastic deformation may play a part in fatigue due to Bauschinger type effects. For instance, for C and S materials, pure torsional tests lead to brittle fractures whilst plastic strains occur when the tubes are tested in pure tension. A clear relationship then appears between yield criterion and I.N.C.F. (fig. 7).

Fig. 6: UD Material. Static criterion and I.N.C.F. curves

Fig. 7: C Material
1: Static criterion
2: Plasticity criterion and I.N.C.F. curves

CONCLUSIONS

Tensile-torsion tests allow the construction of static fracture criteria. These show that the C.L.T. associated to the hypothesis of fracture of composites by the cracking of the first layer is incorrect. In comparison, the insertion of a unidirectional material into a laminate reinforces its properties. The final hypothesis of the first layer is also insufficient, and must be replaced by a more detailed analysis of the fracture.

The I.N.C.F. curves lead to functions similar to those of static fracture if one of the extremes of the cycle is the origin of stress. The passage of the criterion from static fracture to I.N.C.F. curves is strongly influenced by the mean stress. The results clarify the need for experimental and theoretic study of the role played by the angle of disorientation between layers in a laminate, in the reinforcement of a unidirectional material by insertion in the laminate.

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